

CHALLENGES IN CREATING ESP PRIMERS FOR ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT: This thesis deals with finding out implementation of English for specific purposes (ESP) course and identifying the challenges faced by English textbooks in designing an ESP course for first-year students.

KEYWORDS: ESP course, challenges, course design.

INTRODUCTION

The immediate urgency of English is increasingly felt especially relating to the rapid development in science and technology as well as competition in the job market. Improving the competency can be done with emphasis on the needs of learners as a fundamental problem in the design of learning. This is in line with the application of the English for specific purposes (ESP) approach where the learners' needs are the main consideration in determining the learning process and direction so that the achievement of teaching objectives can work effectively and efficiently. This approach particularly focus to assist learners to master English in allocated time and applicable to their field of study, interest, or profession. It can be taught for any fields of science and professions, such as English for law, medicine, engineering, economics, or mathematical sciences, etc. The importance of designing ESP course aims to make the language specifically taught fulfill the language needed in the field to be studied by the learners. Therefore, implementation of ESP is crucial in order to equip students with appropriate language skill.

MAIN BODY

A course is as "an integrated series of teaching-learning experiences, whose ultimate aim is to lead the learners to a particular state of knowledge" (Hutchinson and Waters, 1987, p. 65) Thus, this is a process of planning and setting up courses for the sake of learning a language. In the context of ESP, course design is a process of data collection in preparing effective tasks, activities, and creating the collecting data to prepare effective tasks, activities, and to create the most suitable setting for ESP learners to achieve their goals (Richards, 2001). Thus, ESP learners' needs and expectations should be given more attention. Learners' need, undoubtedly, play an essential role. This means that course design for ESP setting is not a teacher-centered approach. Therefore,

in designing an ESP course ESP teacher's work involves much more than teaching. Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998) propose the term "ESP practitioner" because this definition is more detailed and complete. Key roles of ESP practitioner are distinguished as follows: as teacher, course designer and materials provider, collaborator, researcher, and evaluator. All these roles are somewhat present as the designing process begin to take place. Language courses, whether ESP or GE, are well established through a number of stages. There are five different stages in preparing an ESP course (Dudley-Evans and Johns, 1998, p. 121). They suggest that the stages are cyclical rather than linear and interconnected. The stages are as follows: needs identification and analysis, syllabus design, materials production, teaching, and assessment and evaluation. In the context of first year students in the Engineering Faculty at Termez Institute of Engineering and Technology, English is a mandatory subject to be taken during their initial semesters of study. It consists of four credit hours and is taught twice a week for 15 weeks. Therefore, the English course in the first semester should provide language skills that is applicable not only for their study, for instance to read books or journals written in english, but also for their future after they graduate.

From the interview, it is revealed that the English course given is not a complete ESP course. Teachers implement a course combined mostly with GE and few ESP contents. ESP contents are usually given in forms of texts and vocabulary enrichment. Several challenges inevitably emerged when each stages of the process of designing the course takes place. The teachers identified the challenges related with the stages of course designing.

CONCLUSION

A complete ESP course seems appalling to be designed as teachers have to play several roles simultaneously in order to make the course comes into realization. The teachers are required not only to teach or organize the class to run well, but also prepare syllabus, provide materials, collaborates with subject/content experts, conduct research, and evaluate the students and the course. The result of this study also shows that challenges are inevitable as the teachers proceed to design an ESP course.

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